

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF THE LOCAL EXPOSURE LEVEL DURING
ADULT CHEST X-RAYS**Dr Abdul Rahman¹, Dr Fozia Hussain², Dr Khadija Mariyum³²S.M.B.B, Medical University, Larkana³Rawalpindi Medical University**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Introduction: Diagnostic X-rays represent the major portion of radiation exposure from artificial origin to the general population. **Objectives:** The main objective of the study is to analyse the local exposure level during adult chest X-Rays. **Material and methods:** This descriptive study was conducted in S.M.B.B, Medical University, Larkana during June 2019 to January 2020. The current-time product (mAs) values used in the examinations were collected by the technologists in the rooms included in the survey; prospective data collection did not change the routine workflow in the institution and did not involve any additional radiation exposure to the patients. **Results:** The data was collected from 100 patients. These values are essential parameters in the process of optimizing the dose delivered and the quality of the images. They are directly a function of the high voltage (kV) and the load (mAs). **Conclusion:** It is concluded that an improvement in practices, especially in relation to the technical parameters and protocols associated with strengthening the permanent radiation protection skills of radiological manipulators, could contribute to better radiological protection of patients in this radiology department.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Abdul Rahman,

QR code

Please cite this article in press Abdul Rahman et al, *Assessment Of The Local Exposure Level During Adult Chest X-Rays.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(11).

INTRODUCTION:

Diagnostic X-rays represent the major portion of radiation exposure from artificial origin to the general population. The benefit of the procedure is immediate for the patient, whereas the stochastic risk of low doses of ionizing radiation is very small and at a long term. However, the large collective dose due to medical exposures justifies the application of the radiation protection principles: the dose of radiation must be kept “as low as reasonably achievable” but high enough to obtain the required diagnostic information [1].

Even though use of computed tomography is associated with substantially higher radiation exposure than conventional radiography, general x-ray imaging is still the most frequently used modality in diagnostic radiology. The diagnostic reference level (DRL), or reference values, represent an efficient criterion for radiation protection of patients and optimization of radiographic procedures [2]. The International Commission on Radiological Protection introduced the concept of DRLs as practice guidelines in 1996 [3] to identify the situations where the level of patient dose is unusually high. The entrance surface dose (ESD) was suggested for monitoring in conventional radiography. The European community also has published guidelines on quality criteria and reference levels for diagnostic radiographic images [4].

The medical applications of ionizing radiation have, for many years now, contributed to an improvement of medical practicals and bring a real benefit in terms of health. In radiology, dosimetry and diagnostic quality of images are inseparable. Diagnosis is a function dependent on the quality of the radiological image. Dosimetry could be defined as the measurement of ionizing radiation received or deposited in a medium [4]. Diagnostic medical examinations using ionizing radiation such as radiology, CT, and nuclear medicine lead to variable exposure of patients according to the procedure implemented, the facility of the technology,

and the patient’s morphotype [5]. In view of this, the reality of these risks, however, comes up against the general problem commonly referred to as the problem of low doses. As observed elsewhere, there are also wide variations in the dose for the same type of examination and the same morphotype of X-ray patients. The health effects of doses delivered in radiodiagnostics are not only low but zero below an imprecise threshold since the linear relationship without threshold not based on 0.6% to 3% of cancers would be attributable to radiodiagnostics [6].

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to analyse the local exposure level during adult chest X-Rays.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive study was conducted in S.M.B.B, Medical University, Larkana during June 2019 to January 2020. The current-time product (mAs) values used in the examinations were collected by the technologists in the rooms included in the survey; prospective data collection did not change the routine workflow in the institution and did not involve any additional radiation exposure to the patients. The mAs values, which were equipment and examination specific, were displayed on the x-ray unit console during the examination and recorded by the technologist. A total of 100 adult patients weighing 70 ± 10 kg who had standard examinations during the study period were involved. The examinations were carried out on a General Electric-branded appliance, whose maximum voltage at the terminals is 150 kV. The anthropometric data and the technical parameters used (kV, mAs, FFD, and FSD) were collected at the time of examinations.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 100 patients. These values are essential parameters in the process of optimizing the dose delivered and the quality of the images. They are directly a function of the high voltage (kV) and the load (mAs).

Table 01: Technical values for conduction of exam

Radiography	Incidence	kV	mAs	FFD	FSD	ESD		3 rd quartile	SD
						Min - max	Max/min		
Chest	PA	122–125 (122.8 ± 1.58)	2.4–4 (3.17 ± 0.46)	138–179 (180 ± 0.09)	170–199 (138 ± 0.20)	0.08 – 0.09	1.04	0.18	0.21

Table 02: The ESDs for anthropomorphic phantoms before and after protocols optimization

Examination	National DRL, mGy	Initial ESD, mGy		After adjustment		Local CR DRLs, mGy
		DR	CR	CR ESD, mGy	Change, %	
Chest PA	0.2-0.4	0.09 ± 0.01	0.82 ± 0.14	0.67 ± 0.08	21	0.8
Chest LAT	0.6-1.6	0.28 ± 0.07	3.52 ± 0.61	2.18 ± 0.47	30	2.34

DISCUSSION:

As imaging spreads to the most remote areas of the country, there is an urgent need to optimize work protocols. This optimization of doses delivered to the patients could well be effective by the setting up of a regulatory framework with the obligation of designation and training of humans competent in radioprotection which would allow not only to improve the radioprotection of the patients but also of the personnel, for the establishment of regular dosimetric control and dosimetric standards [7]. The lack of ongoing training of personnel on radiation protection measures could be noted as potential factors of patient exposure [8].

This finding is still very worrying, when the professional profile (nurse and caregivers) of some radiology manipulators does not correspond to their “background” because they are rather converted into radiological manipulators and a large rotation of radiology trainees who find work protocols not available and also who are often forced to produce images capable of being exploited [9]. In view of this, they have either no idea or a rough idea of the good practice in radiodiagnosics or even radiation protection of patients. From these observations, we can affirm with the low level of knowledge in radioprotection in African countries, especially those of sub-Saharan Africa, despite the existence of the laws governing radiation protection and the lack of resources forced to approximate, DRLs [10].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that an improvement in practices, especially in relation to the technical parameters and protocols associated with strengthening the permanent radiation protection skills of radiological manipulators, could contribute to better radiological protection of patients in this radiology department. Moreover, note that the indirect method used here is a reliable alternative for measuring the entrance skin dose of the patient.

REFERENCES:

1. A.B. de González and S. Darby, “Risk of cancer from diagnostic X-rays: estimates for the UK and 14 other countries,” *The Lancet*, vol. 363, no. 9406, pp. 345–351, 2004.
2. R. Azzoz, K. M. ElShahat, R. A. MonemRezk, and R. Monem, “Evaluation of quality control systems for X-ray machines at different hospitals using patient’s radiological dose assessment technology,” *IOSR Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 29–34, 2014.
3. C. J. Olowookere, I. A. Babalola, N. N. Jibiri, R. I. Obed, L. Bamidele, and E. O. Ajetumobi, “A preliminary radiation dose audit in some nigerian hospitals: need for determination of national diagnostic reference levels (NDRLs),” *The Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 87–495, 2012.
4. V. Tsapaki, I. A. Tsalafoutas, I. Chinofoti et al., “Radiation doses to patients undergoing standard radiographic examinations: a comparison between two methods,” *The British Journal of Radiology*, vol. 80, no. 950, pp. 107–112, 2007.
5. M. H. Beauvais, A. Biau, M. Bourguignon, C. Challeton De Vathaire, J. F. Lacronique, and M. Valero, “Optimisation des doses délivrées aux patients en radiologie médicale,” *Rapport Scientifique et Technique*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 143–151, 2002.
6. K. Faulkner, D. A. Broadhead, and R. M. Harrison, “Patient dosimetry measurement methods,” *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 113–123, 1999.
7. A. A. Abu Khair, A. O. Hamza, and N. A. Abbas, “Dose reference levels in radiography for the most common examinations in Sudan,” *Sudan Journal of Medical Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 7–16, 2016.
8. D. Khoshdel-Navi, A. Shabestani-Monfared, M. R. Deevband, R. Abdi, and M. Nabahati, “Local-reference patient dose evaluation in conventional radiography examinations in mazandaran, Iran,” *Journal of Biomedical Physics and Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 61–70, 2016.
9. S. Traoré, “Étude comparative de la dose patient a la dose de référence dans le service de radiologie

et d'imagerie médicale de l'hôpital gabriel touré (HGT) à propos de 70 cas," Université de Bamako, Faculté de Médecine, de Pharmacie et d'Odontostomatologie (FMPOS), Bamako, Mali, 2006, Thèse de Doctorat Médecine.

10. P. Roch, D. Celier, C. Etard, and A. Noel, *Bilan Du Recueil 2011-2012 Des Nrd Par L'irsn Et*

Recommandations D'évolution Du Système Par Le GPMED-ASN, Société Française de Radioprotection, Congrès National de Radioprotection, Tours, France, 2005.